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Navigating Pakistan's Export Future: Forecasting Trends Using ARIMA

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to forecast Pakistan's exports from 2024 to 2030 using historical data from 1990 to 2023. The data is providing a comprehensive view of Pakistan's export trends. The Box-Jenkins methodology was employed, utilizing the ARIMA model for time series forecasting. Prior to modeling, a unit root test was conducted to assess stationarity, which revealed that the export data was non-stationary at its level but became stationary after first differencing. The ARIMA model forecasts an initial increase in exports in the next two years, followed by a decline from 2026 to 2030. This trend is attributed to factors such as global demand fluctuations, rising production costs, and potential domestic challenges. Policy recommendations are provided to mitigate the trade deficit and enhance export competitiveness, including diversification of export sectors, improving trade infrastructure, and implementing energy reforms.

Keywords: Exports; Forecasting; ARIMA Modeling; Box-Jenkins Method; Pakistan.

1. INTRODUCTION

Pakistan's main export commodities include textiles, rice, leather goods, chemicals, and carpets. However, the country's export dynamics are influenced by a range of factors, such as changing global demand, regional competition, economic policies, and local business conditions. These factors add complexity, making it tough to predict export trends. Yet, it's a necessary task for effective planning and policy-making. Studies have shown that seasonal shifts and external economic factors, like exchange rates, trade agreements, and market access, significantly affect export patterns. So, it's important to thoroughly understand these patterns and choose the right forecasting methods to produce reliable export predictions. Pakistan, a developing country with a population exceeding 220 million, relies heavily on agriculture as the backbone of its economy. Since gaining independence in 1947, Pakistan has faced a persistent trade deficit. Despite making progress in both exports and imports, the growth of imports has outpaced that of exports. In recent years, Pakistan's exports have shown a continuous decline. For instance, export revenue was recorded at \$25,171 million in FY2014, but this figure dropped to \$23,041 million by FY2019. Meanwhile, imports have been on the rise, reaching \$55,169 million in FY2019. This amount is more than double the value of exports, highlighting the country's vulnerability in terms of trade deficit and balance of payments (Mehmood et al., 2020). Looking at the historical data, the trade deficit was at US \$-504 million in FY1970-71, which further widened to US \$-2,493 million in FY1990-91—nearly a fivefold increase. The situation worsened, hitting a record high of US \$-30,903 million in FY2017-18. During FY2018, exports grew by a mere 12%, while imports surged by 15.7%. To address this growing imbalance, the new government implemented measures in late 2018 aimed at curbing imports. Consequently, in FY2019, imports fell by 6.8%, and exports saw a minor decline of 2.1% (Syed et al., 2022).

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The downward trend continued into FY2019-20, with exports falling by approximately 6.81%, dropping from \$22.958 billion to \$21.394 billion. Imports, however, showed a significant decline of 18.6%, decreasing from \$54.763 billion to \$44.574 billion during the same period (Pakistan Bureau of Statistics, 2020). There were signs of recovery in FY2021-22. Pakistan's exports surged by 25%, reaching USD 8.23 billion in Q3 (Jan-March) compared to USD 6.57 billion in the same period of the previous year. Cumulatively, in the first nine months of FY2020-21, export proceeds grew by 25% over the same period of the previous fiscal year, totaling USD 23.3 billion (Pakistan Trade Perspective, 2022). However, this improvement was short-lived. From July to April FY2023, exports declined by 11.7%, amounting to US \$23.2 billion, compared to US \$26.2 billion in the same period of the previous year. This drop was mainly due to weak global demand and sluggish domestic economic performance amid demand-curbing measures (Economic Survey of Pakistan, 2023). In the first quarter of 2024 (Jan-Mar), exports were valued at Rs. 2,219,164.09 million, marking a 3% decrease from the previous quarter (Oct-Dec 2023) but an increase of 25.33% over the same period in 2023. In US dollar terms, exports for Jan-Mar 2024 stood at \$7,941.81 million, which is a 1.75% decrease from Oct-Dec 2023 but a 16.92% increase over Jan-Mar 2023. Cumulatively, exports for Jul-Mar 2024 reached Rs. 6,517,925.16 million, up by 31.71% compared to the same period last year. In dollar terms, this amounted to \$22,926.39 million, reflecting an 8.99% increase (Pakistan Bureau of Statistics, 2024). Accurate export forecasting is vital for developing countries like Pakistan as it guides policy-making and economic strategies. Exports contribute significantly to a country's economy by generating foreign exchange, boosting production, and improving employment rates. Given the importance of exports, it has always been a challenge for policymakers to accurately predict export trends. Therefore, employing effective forecasting methods is crucial to support informed decisions that promote sustainable economic development.

Previous research in export forecasting has highlighted the importance of accounting for seasonality, trends, and other key variables to improve prediction accuracy. For developing countries, particularly those heavily dependent on trade, using forecasting models is crucial for crafting strategies to boost exports and reduce trade deficits. Accurate forecasts can help identify market opportunities and competitive advantages, allowing governments to implement supportive policies and incentivize exporters. Ghauri et al. (2020) made a significant contribution by evaluating Pakistan's export trends and providing projections for the fiscal year 2020. Using annual export data from FY2002 to FY2019, their study analyzed potential growth in exports while factoring in seasonal and economic variations. Their research projected an export growth rate of 1.87% for FY2020. The study's findings stressed the need for Pakistan's policymakers to take corrective measures to enhance exports. Recommendations include offering more incentives to exporters, lowering business costs, and improving Pakistan's competitiveness in the global market, especially when compared to regional players like India, Bangladesh, and China. Dave et al. (2021) focused on Indonesia's exports, emphasizing the need for precise export forecasts to aid government decision-making. Accurate forecasting can help in economic policy formulation, enhance trade negotiations, and assist in identifying sectors that need support to boost productivity. By using these forecasts, governments can implement strategic policies aimed at fostering economic growth and preparing for potential challenges in international trade. Ansari Saleh et al. (2022) explored forecasting the value of Indonesia's oil and gas exports. Their study underscored the importance of accurate predictions for guiding future policy-making. Insights into export trends are vital for economic planning, helping policymakers address potential challenges, stabilize revenue streams, and ensure Indonesia's competitiveness in the global oil and gas market. Thus, forecasting export values becomes a key tool for policymakers, equipping them with the necessary information to create supportive policies and manage resources efficiently. Biswas and Islam (2022) highlighted the importance of considering both domestic and global economic indicators in export forecasting. These factors play a crucial role in shaping export strategies and policy decisions. Understanding these relationships is essential for policymakers aiming to support a stable and growing export sector. Accurate forecasts can identify potential risks and opportunities, enabling strategies to maintain equilibrium in the trade market. This is particularly crucial in cases of economic imbalances, where corrective measures are needed to restore a balanced export growth path. Melnychenko et al. (2022) analyzed trade dynamics between Ukraine and Romania from 2005 to 2021, with an emphasis on the period following the EU-Ukraine Association Agreement in 2015. The study highlighted the significance of capturing monthly and seasonal variations in export data to produce accurate forecasts. Their findings showed that incorporating historical trade dynamics and seasonal fluctuations can result in forecasts with minimal errors, providing valuable information for policymakers to adjust trade strategies and respond effectively to changes in the global market. Srisuradetchai (2023) explored the complexities of forecasting agricultural exports in Thailand, particularly durian exports. The study emphasized the importance of using interval forecasts to better capture market uncertainties. Agricultural export activities often experience seasonal and trend-driven variations, so providing a forecast interval gives decision-makers insights into potential changes in export values. This information supports strategic planning and market positioning. Accurate interval forecasting is particularly beneficial for agricultural products, as it offers a range of possible outcomes rather than relying solely on a single estimate, aiding exporters and policymakers in navigating market dynamics. Wang (2011) examined Taiwan's export forecasting challenges, highlighting the dynamic nature of export trends and the impact of external economic factors. The study found that while external variables significantly influence export performance initially, their impact lessens over time. This suggests that short-term exports are sensitive to global market conditions, but long-term trends tend to stabilize. Wang also noted the importance of sample period length in forecasting accuracy. Short-term forecasts benefit from specific methodologies that can handle limited datasets and adapt to immediate market changes. On the other hand, long-term forecasts are more accurate when they capture a broad range of historical data, reflecting underlying trends over time. Sahu et al. (2024) analyzed the growth, sustainability, and export behavior of Indian potatoes from 1966 to 2020. The study highlighted that, despite growth in production, India's average potato productivity remains significantly lower than the global best, indicating a potential area for policy improvement. The research also emphasized the seasonal and lag-dependent nature of potato prices in India. Understanding these seasonal trends is crucial for exporters and policymakers to develop strategies that maximize market presence during high-demand periods and mitigate risks during low-price seasons. Additionally, the study revealed that future import patterns of Indian potatoes in key markets might decline, signaling the need for strategic market diversification and stronger trade relations. Sohrabpour et al. (2021)

advocated moving beyond traditional time series methods to adopt advanced techniques that capture the complexities of export markets. Their study suggested that incorporating causal factors into forecasting models can lead to more accurate and actionable insights. By understanding the variables driving export sales, businesses can better anticipate market changes, adjust strategies, and optimize supply chains. The literature emphasizes that export sales forecasting is not just about predicting future quantities, but also about understanding market dynamics. Firms using advanced forecasting techniques can identify potential opportunities and risks in international markets, leading to proactive decisions in marketing, production, and logistics, ultimately improving resource management, reducing costs, and enhancing global competitiveness.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY

2.1. Variables of its Measurements

In this study, the variable to be forecasted is Pakistan's exports, denoted by the symbol X and measured in millions of USD. The data for this analysis spans from 1990 to 2023 and is sourced from the World Development Indicators. To begin, a unit root test will be conducted to check the stationarity of the data. Following this, the Box-Jenkins methodology will be applied to forecast export values from 2024 to 2030.

2.2. Unit Root Test

A Unit Root Test is a statistical method used in econometrics to determine if a time series dataset is non-stationary and contains a unit root. If a unit root is present, it means the variable is affected by random shocks and doesn't revert to a long-term average, indicating a lack of stability or consistent trend over time. These tests are crucial in econometric analysis to ensure economic data is modeled correctly. Commonly used unit root tests include the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test and the Phillips-Perron (PP) test.

2.2.1. The Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF)

The Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test is a widely used statistical method for detecting a unit root in a time series, which helps in identifying if the series is non-stationary. It extends the original Dickey-Fuller test by including lagged differences of the dependent variable to address higher-order autocorrelation. The ADF test can also include an intercept and an optional trend component, making it capable of capturing more complex patterns in the data. By accounting for these factors, the ADF test provides a more robust and reliable evaluation of whether a time series is non-stationary.

To test for a unit root in the variables with an intercept but without a trend, the ADF equation takes the following form:

$$\Delta PCI = \alpha + \gamma X_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^k \delta_i \Delta X_{t-1} + \varepsilon_t \quad (1)$$

Further, to test for a unit root in the specified variables with an intercept and trend, the following will be the form of the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) equation:

$$\Delta X_t = \alpha + \beta_t + \gamma X_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^k \delta_i \Delta X_{t-1} + \varepsilon_t \quad (2)$$

2.3. Box and Jenkins Method

The Box-Jenkins method is a popular approach for time series forecasting, mainly used to identify, estimate, and diagnose ARIMA (Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average) models. This method helps in predicting future values based on historical data. The process begins with collecting historical data and then checking for stationarity, applying differencing if needed. Next, the Autocorrelation Function (ACF) and Partial Autocorrelation Function (PACF) plots are analyzed to identify the appropriate parameters (p, d, q) for the model. Once the model is fitted, diagnostic checks are performed on the residuals to ensure they resemble white noise. If the residuals pass these checks, the model is ready for forecasting.

The ARIMA model can be mathematically represented as:

$$\Delta X = \varphi_1 \Delta X_{t-1} + \dots + \varphi_p \Delta X_{t-p} + \theta_1 \varepsilon_{t-1} + \dots + \theta_q \varepsilon_{t-q} + \varepsilon_t \quad (3)$$

Where Δ is the differencing operator, ϕ are the AR parameters, θ are the MA parameters, and ε_t is the error term.

2.4. ARIMA Model Overview

The ARIMA model is defined by three parameters: (p, d, q).

- **p:** The number of lag observations included in the model (autoregressive part).
- **d:** The number of times that the raw observations are differenced (integrated part).
- **q:** The size of the moving average window (moving average part).

Key Equations

1. AR (Autoregressive) Component:

$$X_t = \varphi_1 X_{t-1} + \dots + \varphi_p X_{t-p} + \varepsilon_t \quad (4)$$

- ϕ represents the parameters of the model.
- ε_t is the white noise error term.

2. **I (Integrated) Component:**

- Differencing d times to achieve stationarity:

3. **MA (Moving Average) Component:**

$$X_t = \theta_1 \varepsilon_{t-1} + \dots + \theta_q \varepsilon_{t-q} + \varepsilon_t \tag{5}$$

- θ are the parameters for the moving average part.

Combining these components, the ARIMA model can be expressed as:

$$\Delta X = \varphi_1 \Delta X_{t-1} + \dots + \varphi_p \Delta X_{t-p} + \theta_1 \varepsilon_{t-1} + \dots + \theta_q \varepsilon_{t-q} + \varepsilon_t \tag{6}$$

2.4.1. The Q-statistic(Ljung-Box test)

The Q-statistic, based on the Ljung-Box test, is a diagnostic tool used to assess the adequacy of ARIMA models by checking for autocorrelation in the residuals. After fitting an ARIMA model, the residuals should ideally behave like white noise, meaning they should not exhibit any significant autocorrelation. The Ljung-Box test examines whether a group of autocorrelations up to a certain lag differs significantly from zero. A low p-value (typically less than 0.05) indicates that the residuals are autocorrelated, suggesting that the model has not fully captured the data's dynamics. Conversely, if the p-values are high, the null hypothesis that the residuals are uncorrelated cannot be rejected, meaning the model is a good fit. This test is crucial in validating that the ARIMA model is correctly specified and reliable for forecasting.

2.4.2. ARMA Diagnostic View

The "Inverse Roots of AR/MA Polynomials" diagnostic plot is used to assess the stability and invertibility of an ARIMA model. In this test, the inverse roots of the autoregressive (AR) and moving average (MA) polynomials are plotted on the complex plane. For the ARIMA model to be stable and produce reliable forecasts, all the inverse roots must lie inside the unit circle (a circle with a radius of 1). If any roots fall outside the unit circle, the model is considered unstable or non-invertible, meaning it may not be suitable for forecasting. Therefore, this diagnostic ensures that the model is well-specified and can be trusted for future predictions.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Table 1 shows the descriptive statistics show that the dataset has an average (mean) of 20,110.12, indicating relatively high values overall. The median is 20,859.83, slightly higher than the mean, which points to a slight positive skew in the data. This is further supported by the skewness value of 0.117, suggesting that the distribution is fairly symmetrical.

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics of Pakistan's Exports

Mean	Median	Maximum	Minimum	Std. Dev.	Skewness	Kurtosis
20110.12	20859.83	39515.65	5917.029	10048.4	0.116871	1.541301

The data ranges from a minimum of 5,917.03 to a maximum of 39,515.65, indicating a significant spread in values. The standard deviation, at 10,048.4, reveals considerable variation around the mean. With a kurtosis value of 1.541, the distribution has lighter tails and is less peaked than a normal distribution, suggesting a flatter spread of values. Table 2 shows the unit root estimates.

Table 2: Unit Root Test Results

Variable	Level		1st Difference		Decision
	Intercept	Intercept & Trend	Intercept	Intercept & Trend	
Exports	-0.572307	-2.375771	-5.888448	-5.786701	I(1)
	0.8636	0.3846	0	0.0002	

The unit root test (The Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) Test) results show that the variable "X" is non-stationary on level, as the p-values for both the intercept and intercept with trend are not significant. However, after taking the first difference, the test statistics become highly significant, indicating that "Exports" is stationary at first difference. Figure 1 shows the correlogram for ready reference.

Sample: 1990 2023

Included observations: 34

Autocorrelation	Partial Correlation	AC	PAC	Q-Stat	Prob	
		1	0.905	0.905	30.408	0.000
		2	0.797	-0.125	54.721	0.000
		3	0.733	0.190	75.914	0.000
		4	0.671	-0.061	94.304	0.000
		5	0.588	-0.112	108.89	0.000
		6	0.508	-0.010	120.17	0.000
		7	0.447	0.009	129.24	0.000
		8	0.376	-0.111	135.88	0.000
		9	0.289	-0.088	139.96	0.000
		10	0.198	-0.108	141.95	0.000
		11	0.097	-0.170	142.45	0.000
		12	-0.011	-0.125	142.46	0.000
		13	-0.118	-0.125	143.27	0.000
		14	-0.186	0.097	145.39	0.000
		15	-0.249	-0.093	149.37	0.000
		16	-0.309	0.017	155.85	0.000

Figure 1: Correlogram

Source: Author's work.

The correlogram indicates that an AR(1) and MA(3) model might be suitable for this series. The noticeable spike at lag 1 in both the autocorrelation (AC) and partial autocorrelation (PAC) suggests the inclusion of an AR(1) component, capturing the immediate autocorrelation in the data. The gradual decline in autocorrelations beyond lag 1, along with the significant spike at lag 3 in the partial autocorrelation, points to the need for a moving average (MA) component at lag 3. The AR(1) component will capture the immediate relationships, while the MA(3) will account for the influence of random shocks over three periods. Since the correlogram shows no clear trend or need for differencing, the differencing order (d) is likely 0, resulting in an ARIMA(1,0,3) model for this time series. Table 3 shows the OLS regression estimate.

Table 3: OLS Regression Estimates

Dependent Variable: X				
Method: ARMA Maximum Likelihood (OPG - BHHH)				
Sample: 1990 2023				
Included observations: 34				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	21225.38	10652.46	1.992534	0.0555
AR(1)	0.969383	0.074153	13.07279	0.0000
MA(3)	0.447764	0.179889	2.489108	0.0186
SIGMASQ	5373658	1151883	4.665109	0.0001
Statistical Tests				
R-squared	0.945167	F-statistic		172.3723
Adjusted R-squared	0.939684	Prob(F-statistic)		0.000
Inverted AR Roots	0.97	Durbin-Watson stat		1.961238

The results from the ARMA maximum likelihood estimation for the dependent variable (Exports) from 1990 to 2023 show a strong model fit, as indicated by an (R^2) of 0.945 and an adjusted (R^2) of 0.940. The constant term (C) is estimated at 21,225.38 with a p-value of 0.0555, suggesting marginal significance. The autoregressive component AR(1) is highly significant with a coefficient of 0.969, indicating strong persistence in the series. The moving average term MA(3) is also significant with a coefficient of 0.448, suggesting that past forecast errors influence current values. The estimated variance of the error term (SIGMASQ) is 5,373,658, with a p-value of 0.0001, confirming its significance. The Durbin-Watson statistic of 1.961 indicates minimal autocorrelation in the residuals. The F-statistic of 172.3723, with a p-value of 0, confirms that the model as a whole is statistically significant. The inverted AR roots (0.97) and complex MA roots suggest stability in the model. Overall, the model demonstrates strong explanatory power and statistical significance, indicating it effectively captures the dynamics of the variable (Exports). Figure 2 shows the Q-statistic via Ljung-Box Test.

Sample: 1990 2030
 Included observations: 34
 Q-statistic probabilities adjusted for 2 ARMA terms

Autocorrelation	Partial Correlation	AC	PAC	Q-Stat	Prob	
		1	-0.100	-0.100	0.3722	
		2	-0.160	-0.172	1.3525	
		3	-0.030	-0.068	1.3870	0.239
		4	0.114	0.078	1.9134	0.384
		5	-0.051	-0.045	2.0222	0.568
		6	-0.097	-0.083	2.4331	0.657
		7	0.090	0.066	2.7980	0.731
		8	-0.095	-0.125	3.2215	0.781
		9	-0.060	-0.066	3.3988	0.846
		10	-0.016	-0.046	3.4114	0.906
		11	0.178	0.129	5.1029	0.825
		12	-0.139	-0.113	6.1740	0.800
		13	-0.162	-0.147	7.7066	0.739
		14	0.053	-0.030	7.8754	0.795
		15	0.009	-0.080	7.8807	0.851
		16	0.096	0.110	8.5130	0.861

Figure 2: The Q-statistic (Ljung-Box test)

Source: Author's work.

The correlogram of residuals displays the autocorrelation (AC) and partial autocorrelation (PAC) for up to 16 lags of the residuals from the fitted ARIMA model. The Q-statistic (Ljung-Box test) and corresponding p-values (Prob) help assess the independence of residuals at each lag. In this case, the autocorrelations and partial autocorrelations are mostly close to zero, and none of the Q-statistic p-values are below the standard significance level (0.05), suggesting that the residuals are not significantly autocorrelated. This indicates that the ARIMA model has successfully captured the underlying structure of the data, and the residuals behave like white noise, meaning the model fits the data well and is appropriate for forecasting. Figure 3 shows the ARMA diagnostic view.

Figure 3: ARMA Diagnostic View

Source: Author's work.

The graph illustrates the inverse roots of the AR and MA polynomials for the ARIMA model, which are used to check the model's stationarity and invertibility. For the model to be stationary (regarding AR terms) and invertible (for MA terms), the roots must lie inside the unit circle. In this case, both the AR root (shown in blue) and the MA roots (in red) are either within or right on the boundary of the unit circle. This indicates that the ARIMA model is stable, stationary, and invertible. Since there are no roots outside the circle, the

specified AR(1) and MA(3) model appears to have no stability issues. Figure 4 shows the exports forecast trend in Pakistan.

Figure 4: Exports Forecast Estimates

Note: XF shows exports forecast. Source: Author’s work.

Figure 4 shows the exports forecast (XF) for a time series using the ARIMA model, with projections from 2024 to 2030. The blue line represents the predicted values of the series, while the red dashed lines indicate the confidence interval, set at ± 2 standard errors (S.E.), which gives a 95% confidence interval around the forecast. The forecast starts around 40 in 2024, with a slight dip in 2025, after which the trend becomes relatively stable and slightly declining until 2030. The widening of the confidence interval over time reflects increased uncertainty in the forecast as it projects further into the future. Figure 5 shows the overall forecast exports trend for ready reference.

Figure 5: Overall Exports Forecast Curve

Note: XF shows exports forecast. Source: Author’s work.

Figure 5 illustrates the historical and forecasted values of Pakistan’s exports from 1990 to 2030. The red line (X) shows the actual exports from 1990 to 2023, highlighting a steady upward trend with periodic fluctuations, including a significant spike around 2020–2021, likely due to global disruptions such as the COVID-19 pandemic. After 2023, the blue line (XF) represents the forecasted exports, which show a slight increase initially, peaking around 2025, followed by a gradual decline up to 2030. This projected dip may reflect challenges such as weakening global demand, rising production costs, or other economic constraints that could slow down export growth after 2025. Table 4 shows the Pakistan’s exports forecast trend from 2024 to 2030.

Table 4: Forecast Exports Trend (2024-20230)

Years	Forecast Exports (XF)
2024	35855.9101
2025	38886.2888
2026	37220.17154
2027	36730.45393
2028	36255.73016
2029	35795.54116
2030	35349.44192

The forecast for Pakistan's exports from 2024 to 2030 indicates an initial increase, peaking in 2025 at 38,886.29, likely reflecting improved market conditions and increased global demand. However, this is followed by a gradual decline, suggesting potential challenges such as market saturation, economic volatility, or external factors like changing trade policies. The decreasing trend in subsequent years may imply that while the short-term outlook is optimistic, long-term projections should account for risks such as political instability or global economic fluctuations that could impact export performance. Overall, the forecast captures both the potential for growth and the necessity for caution in the face of evolving economic conditions.

4. CONCLUSIONS

This study aims to forecast Pakistan's exports from 2024 to 2030, using data from 1990 to 2023 as a foundation. The dataset was sourced from World Development Indicators (WDI). To generate reliable forecasts, stationarity of the data was checked by The Augmented Dickey Fuller (ADF) test. The results of the test indicated that the export series was non-stationary at level, meaning that the statistical properties of the series changed over time. However, after applying first differencing, the series became stationary. The Box and Jenkins Method (Auto Regressive Integrated Moving Average methodology) was employed to forecast the Exports of Pakistan as it is well-regarded for time series forecasting due to its systematic approach to modeling based on historical patterns. By ensuring stationarity, the ARIMA model can now accurately capture the underlying patterns in the historical exports data, which is essential for producing robust forecasts for Pakistan's exports in the coming years. The ARIMA model forecast suggests an initial increase in Pakistan's exports during the first two years, followed by a gradual decline after 2025. This short-term rise in exports could be due to anticipated improvements in global demand and favorable trade agreements that may temporarily boost export performance. However, the expected decline after 2025 might be linked to several factors, including potential global economic slowdowns, challenges in maintaining competitiveness in key export industries, and domestic issues like rising production costs or energy shortages. Moreover, changes in trade policies or disruptions in major markets, such as geopolitical tensions or shifting consumer preferences, could also negatively impact Pakistan's export potential in the longer term. The widening confidence intervals in the forecast highlight the growing uncertainty about these future conditions.

To enhance Pakistan's export performance, several policy recommendations are proposed. First, it's crucial to diversify the export base beyond traditional sectors like textiles. The government should promote high-value industries such as information technology, pharmaceuticals, engineering goods, and agro-processed products. Encouraging innovation and improving product quality in these sectors will be key. Second, improving trade infrastructure is essential. Modernizing ports, enhancing transportation networks, and streamlining customs procedures can help reduce costs and expedite trade. Investing in digital infrastructure to facilitate e-commerce is equally important. Third, reforms in the energy sector are necessary to improve reliability and reduce costs for exporters. Investing in renewable energy can play a significant role in achieving this goal. Additionally, pursuing favorable bilateral and multilateral trade agreements with major partners, like China and the EU, and renegotiating existing deals to secure better market access can help open up new markets. Further, enhancing support programs for exporters through tax incentives, export financing, and targeted training can strengthen competitiveness. Revisiting trade policies to lower tariffs on essential raw materials while controlling unnecessary luxury imports can also help in reducing the trade deficit. Lastly, establishing export-oriented industrial clusters can create economies of scale, boost productivity, and attract foreign direct investment. Together, these measures aim to strengthen Pakistan's export sector, making it more competitive in global markets and helping to address the trade deficit.

Ethical approval

All international standards have been adopted and compliance.

Informed consent

The study was conducted with equal participation by all authors.

Conflicts of interests

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interests.

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Data and materials availability

All data associated with this study are present in the paper.

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